

Breastfeeding Experiences of Working Mothers in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Exclusive breastfeeding refers to providing infants with breast milk exclusively for the first six months, without any additional food or fluids, aside from authorized vitamins and medications. It is a natural process that significantly impacts the health of the baby, mother, and family. However, many mothers face challenges in successfully breastfeeding or often stop early, particularly working mothers. This study aimed to explore the breastfeeding experiences of working mothers. Using a qualitative phenomenological approach, the research involved eight participants who are working mothers with babies aged 3-6 months, selected through purposive sampling. Data analysis was conducted using Colaizzi's method and NVIVO software. The findings revealed six key categories: the process of pregnancy and childbirth, self-confidence, breastfeeding challenges, strategies to overcome these challenges, sources of breastfeeding support, and emotional experiences during breastfeeding. The study highlights the crucial need for support from family, the workplace (including colleagues, supervisors, and available facilities) to enhance the success of exclusive breastfeeding among working mothers.

KEYWORDS: Exclusive Breastfeeding, Experience, Working Mother.

INTRODUCTION

The Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) is a key indicator of a country's welfare. The goal for 2030 is to eliminate preventable deaths among newborns and children under five, with all nations striving to lower the Neonatal Mortality Rate to at least 12 per 1,000 live births and the Toddler Mortality Rate to 25 per 1,000 live births (SDGs, Goal 3). According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the global strategy for infant and young child feeding emphasizes that preventing infant mortality can be achieved through proper feeding practices. This includes exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life and the introduction of safe and nutritious complementary foods starting at six months, while continuing to breastfeed until the age of two or beyond (WHO, 2023).

Breast milk is a natural source of nutrition for infants, composed of a fat emulsion that is easily digestible and produced by the mother's mammary glands through the lactation process. It serves as the primary nutritional intake for newborns, specifically for those aged 0 to 6 months, during which exclusive breastfeeding is recommended. Exclusively breastfed babies are less likely to experience infectious diseases, asthma attacks, and allergies, as well as having a lower risk of obesity and malnutrition.

Based on data obtained by the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) (2012) Exclusive breastfeeding coverage in the world averages 38%. Data from the Basic Health Research in Dewanti et al (2022) indicates that only 52.5% of the 2.3 million infants under six months old in Indonesia received exclusive breastfeeding, marking a 12% decline from 2019. Additionally, the rate of early breastfeeding initiation (IMD) fell from 58.2% in 2019 to 48.6% in 2021. West Nusa Tenggara reported the highest exclusive breastfeeding coverage at 87.35%, while Papua had the lowest at 15.32%. According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, the percentage of infants under six months exclusively breastfed was 70.86% in 2020, which declined to 65.63% in 2021 before rising again to 67.22% in 2022 (WHO, 2022).

Breastfeeding is a natural process that plays a crucial role in the health and well-being of babies, mothers, and families. Despite its importance, many mothers struggle to initiate or continue breastfeeding, often citing various challenges, including the demands of employment. To promote exclusive breastfeeding in Indonesia, the government has implemented Law No. 36 of 2009, Article 128, which asserts a baby's right to receive exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life. This law emphasizes the need for family, governmental, local authorities, and community support to provide mothers with the necessary time and facilities to breastfeed effectively.

Research by Vilar (2021) indicates that the lack of exclusive breastfeeding among infants is often linked to working mothers. Those who work over eight hours a day may find it challenging to have enough time to breastfeed or express milk. This time constraint

poses a significant barrier to exclusive breastfeeding for employed mothers, despite efforts from supervisors and colleagues to allow them time to express milk.

While breastfeeding is a natural process, not all mothers are able to exclusively breastfeed their infants. Numerous factors affect the ability to practice exclusive breastfeeding, warranting further investigation. This has prompted researchers to explore the breastfeeding experiences of working mothers. The aim of this study is to examine the breastfeeding experiences of working mothers at X Jakarta Hospital in Indonesia.

METHOD

This research uses qualitative research with a descriptive phenomenological approach with in-depth interviews for 30-40 minutes and using an interview guide and recorded using a digital recorder. This research was conducted at “X” Hospital Jakarta, Indonesia in September 2023- January 2024. The sampling technique used purposive sampling technique, as many as 8 participants. Data analysis using the Collaizzi method with the help of Nvivo R1 software to perform data management and data analysis (thematic analysis).

RESULT AND DISCLAIMER

A. Informant Characteristics

Table 1. Characteristics of the Informant

Name	Years	Education	Number Children	of Youngest Child's age	Job
P1	33	Bachelor	3 people	3 months	Nurse
P2	29	Bachelor	1 people	4 months	Nurse
P3	28	Diploma	1 people	5 months	Nurse
P4	28	Diploma	1 people	3 months	Pharmacy Officer
P5	33	Bachelor	2 people	4 months	Nurse
P6	23	Senior School	High 1 people	6 months	Cleaning Service
P7	28	Diploma	2 people	3 months	Nutritionist
P8	26	Diploma	2 people	3 months	Nurse

The majority of participants in the study worked as nurses with Diploma 3 Nursing and Bachelor of Nursing education levels. In addition, breastfeeding mothers who became respondents in this study were pharmacy officers (1 mother), nutritionists (1 mother), and cleaning service (1 mother). All participants were breastfeeding mothers with ages ranging from 23 years to 33 years. The majority of them had one child (1 mother). Some participants had 2 children (3 mothers) and 3 children (1 mother). Their children ranged in age from 3 months to 6 months.

B. Results of Research Analysis

Based on the results of data analysis, there were six main themes that showed the breastfeeding experience of working mothers, namely the process of pregnancy or childbirth, self-confidence, obstacles to breastfeeding, efforts to overcome breastfeeding obstacles, breastfeeding support, and emotions. These themes can be visualized and explained in detail in the following sections.

Source: NVivo Data Processing

Figure 1. NVivo model Breastfeeding experiences of working mothers

Theme 1: Pregnancy and childbirth process

The process of pregnancy or childbirth certainly has problems and also ways to overcome these problems. The experience of dealing with these problems is certainly different for each mother. The same goes for the ways to overcome these problems.

"...At 37 weeks of pregnancy, there was a problem during the ultrasound. They said the circumference of her abdomen did not match the age of the baby." (P1)

"...When the labor was controlled, the water was a little, on ultrasound also from the computer it was 3.5 kg. Doctor Syafriani suggested induction." (P2)

"...From this first pregnancy, until about 4 months, I felt drunk, nauseous, had no appetite, and lost weight." (P4)

"...There was a factor of hypertension during pregnancy so it had to be born, it had to be controlled at that time, it became severe preeclampsia from the doctor." (P8)

The process of pregnancy and childbirth is a process that a mother must go through before going through the process of breastfeeding. During the process of pregnancy and childbirth, a mother is certainly influenced by factors and conditions that are different for each mother. The experience of participants in this study is the process of pregnancy and childbirth which involves 2 factors, namely pregnancy and labour problems and the process of Early Breastfeeding Initiation /Skin to Skin Contact (SSC).

Some participants revealed that there were obstacles during the process of pregnancy and childbirth such as pre eclampsia and premature baby conditions allowed mothers not to be able to do Early Breastfeeding Initiation or SSC, but there were some participants who also carried out the IMD or SSC process. In several studies on Early Breastfeeding Initiation including: that not doing Early Breastfeeding Initiation results in decreased breast milk production due to reduced stimulation of infant suction, not doing Early Breastfeeding Initiation can cause problems with the breastfeeding process and milk production in the mother, while babies who are given the opportunity to IMD are 8 times more successful in exclusive breastfeeding (Abihail & Mahmudiono, 2022).

Theme 2: Confident

Self-confidence is an important asset for mothers in the breastfeeding process. This capital is certainly formed by knowledge, availability of breast milk, and information obtained, both before and after childbirth.

"...So the breast milk hasn't come out yet on the third day... the second or third day I forget, but the DBF continues, meaning that it is still given to the child." (P5)

"...Pumping often." (P6)

"...The first time I installed it was almost 200 ml (160 - 180 ml)" (P4)

"...Not necessarily, sometimes 100 to 180 is the most" (P2)

"...Searching for the right way to breastfeed, after that I never did it again." (P2)

"...First, when I came home, I was taught by the midwife and (neo nurse), to massage (while demonstrating) the tip of the nipple, suck it, pump it often, and finally it came out. Finally I did it, Alhamdulillah it came out." (P3)

"...Drinking milk is what ... milk from ... the mum uung ASI Booster." (P6)

Self-confidence is an important asset for mothers in the breastfeeding process. This capital is certainly formed by the level of maternal knowledge, the amount of milk production produced in each mother, and the information obtained by the mother (Ratnasari, 2019). The experience of participants in this study was that the mother's confidence during the breastfeeding process was influenced by the mother's level of knowledge, as well as the amount of breast milk production. Breast milk production produced by each mother is different, breast milk production is influenced by several factors, including psychological factors. Mothers who are depressed, sad, and lack confidence and various forms of emotional tension will reduce the volume of breast milk, husband support also affects the emotional condition of the mother which can affect the amount of breast milk production (Purnamasari, 2022). Mothers who have enough breast milk to meet the needs of their babies can build self-confidence (Rihi et al, 2020).

Lack of knowledge is another factor that causes a lack of confidence in the breastfeeding process. Knowledge or cognitive is very important in shaping a person's actions, one of which is the inadequate knowledge of mothers regarding the importance of exclusive breastfeeding which makes the cause or problem in exclusive breastfeeding (Handayani, 2023).

Theme 3: Obstacles for breastfeeding mothers

Participants in this study revealed that they had various obstacles in the breastfeeding process. This can be seen from the child, mother, and environmental factors. The two factors can be visualized and explained in detail as follows:

1. Sub-theme: Child Factor

"...Because there is a condition where the child wants to breastfeed continuously... what is it? Growth Spurt..." (P4)

"...Initially I was given interlac, aged 0-2 months, I was given interlac because he was colicky..., I was allergic to cow's milk, it turns out he was allergic to it" (P2).

"...From the doctor, because her weight was tight, she was afraid of being underweight... low... it was recommended to mix formula milk" (P3).

"...Her breathing was unstable so the first breastfeeding was the next night" (P4).

"...How come this baby keeps sleeping... it's hard to breastfeed right" (P8)

"...When the sugar was checked, it turned out to be low right... the doctor gave me breast milk... I was given breast milk" (P8).

2. Sub theme: Maternal Factors

Participants in this study mostly experienced obstacles in the breastfeeding process. The causes of these obstacles are breast milk that does not come out immediately, inverted nipple (sinking nipple), working mothers, nipple blisters, swollen breasts (engorgement), small amount of milk production, and lack of knowledge.

"...The obstacle is that if for example the first time you breastfeed, the milk doesn't come out immediately (P7).

"...So the milk hasn't come out yet, only on the 3rd day it came out." (P5)

"...Between the right and left nipples, there is one that is 'pendelep'" (P1)

"...The first is that my nipple doesn't come out, the nipple is like an inward model" (P3).

"...Because the intensity of our work is very high ... because sometimes it doesn't feel good with friends lah all kinds of things, so it's easy later, later ... later make this deh stone in the breast milk hard" (P8).

"...But the most basic thing in my opinion is ee... We have a clash between my employees, we only get 3 months of leave... It's 3 months ... one and a half we have to take at ... at the beginning even though at the beginning, in my opinion, it can be more delayed like for example one month before we give birth ... we have to take one and a half so the time for us to prepare like breast milk stock if we are working mothers is difficult in my opinion" (P1).

"...Yes, if I'm busy, I don't have time to pump, so it's late, so it becomes mastitis" (P3).

"...Because the first child's experience is less ... less knowledge, less knowledge, so the term is wanting until ... yes at least up to 1 year ... not bad" (P8).

"...Because there is a condition where the child wants to breastfeed continuously... what is it? Growth spurt..." (P4)

"...That's why when you say "Formula" deh, I was really sad, actually how come this is the case, how come my parents don't support it" (P7).

Participants in this study revealed that they had various obstacles in the breastfeeding process. This can be seen from child, mother, and environmental factors. Participants revealed that the obstacle in the breastfeeding process from the child factor was the frequency of breastfeeding children who were more frequent in the first 3 months of age (growth spurt). growth spurt phase or growth acceleration which is a stage that generally occurs during the child's first year (Faristasari, 2019). This growth spurt condition causes mothers to feel anxious and tired because they always think about the availability of their milk or their inability to meet the needs of their children, which can lead to decreased milk production (Faristasari, 2019).

In addition, breastfeeding mothers may experience colic due to allergies caused by consuming cow's milk, underweight children, and hypoglycaemia due to prematurity. These medical conditions force doctors to provide therapy (medicines) and additional formula milk within a certain period of time. This is an obstacle in the process of exclusive breastfeeding where the definition of exclusive breastfeeding itself is the provision of breast milk given to babies for the first six months without providing additional food or other liquids, except vitamins and drugs that have been authorized for consumption (Simanjuntak, 2022).

Most of the participants experienced obstacles in the breastfeeding process. The causes of these obstacles are breast milk that does not come out immediately, inverted nipple (sinking nipple), working mothers, nipple blisters, swollen breasts (engorgement), small amount of milk production, and lack of knowledge.

The obstacle of breast milk not coming out in the breastfeeding process is one of the factors that cause failure in exclusive breastfeeding (Idawati, 2021). Breast milk that has not come out on the first day of birth is a natural process. The production process until the milk fills the breast is one to three days. Therefore, mothers do not need to worry if the milk has not come out or only a little in the first days. A healthy full-term newborn baby has a supply of calories and fluid that can sustain it without drink for several days (Saidah, 2022). Another obstacle during breastfeeding is the inverted nipple. In this condition, it is difficult for the mother to breastfeed her baby because the milk does not come out immediately, causing the baby to fuss easily. This condition occurs because the baby does not get enough milk (Alifah, 2023).

Participants also revealed another obstacle, namely working mothers. Working mothers have high work intensity and short leave periods. This is an obstacle in the breastfeeding process because the lack of time to empty the breasts results in a decrease in the amount of milk production (Saraha, 2020).

Participants also revealed another obstacle they experienced during breastfeeding, which was nipple chafing. Nipple chafing is one of the obstacles for breastfeeding mothers. It occurs due to sore or painful nipples, and poor attachment. Correction of position and attachment are the most common empirical recommendations for the management of nipple pain problems (Fauziah, 2022). Participants also revealed that another obstacle in the breastfeeding process was engorgement (swollen breasts). This occurs due to, among others, increased milk production, early breastfeeding delay, poor attachment, infrequent milk release, and restrictions on breastfeeding time (Rahayu, 2020). Lack of knowledge is another factor that causes obstacles in the breastfeeding process. This happens because of the mother's lack of experience. One of them is the inadequate knowledge of mothers regarding the importance of exclusive breastfeeding which makes the cause or problem in exclusive breastfeeding (Handayani, 2023).

In addition, participants mentioned other obstacles in the breastfeeding process, namely environmental factors such as lack of support from the closest environment, especially family, and lack of proper knowledge and information about breastfeeding. According to (Saraha, 2020), family support is a factor that influences success in exclusive breastfeeding if a mother gets positive support, it will strengthen her belief that the action of providing exclusive breastfeeding to the baby is right. Breastfeeding requires a stable emotional state, considering that the mother's psychological factors greatly affect milk production.

Theme 4: Efforts to overcome breastfeeding obstacles

Obstacles to breastfeeding are a big problem for mothers and their babies. Participants in this study had various efforts to overcome these obstacles. These efforts included breastfeeding only, nipple tugging, pumping, stress management, time management, using

breast milk, improving attachment position, using creams or ointments or coconut oil, using baby saliva, compresses, oxytocin massage, drinking breast milk boosters.

"...But still DBF continues, meaning that it is still given to the child." (P5)

"...He refused but I gave him a lot. So naturally he... what the hell... formed." (P1)

"...Oh I often what... massage it (massaging the nipple) and then the nipple is... Then the nipple is... Like pulled out by hand like that." (P1)

"...Finally, I forced the syringe to pull the colostrum out, and then injected it into the baby." (P3)

"...It's pumped manually." (P6)

"...So it is prioritized to finish first, then the mother after that immediately pumps" (P2).

"...When I have time to rest, for example, I can pump... I can, but if not, then after I work, maybe I pump" (P5).

"...We only get 3 months of leave, 1.5 we have to take at the beginning when we could have taken it later to prepare breast milk stocks" (P1).

"...I'm pumping using the hands-free one" (P4)

"...Then, for example, if it's already blistered, just apply breast milk" (P1).

"...It's just being used, the breast milk is smeared like that" (P4).

"...Yes... Start studying again, learn to watch videos, searching how to breastfeed properly." (P2)

"...Ee... if what I do when the nipple bleeds is to use colostrum liquid, keep breastfeeding because the information from the baby's saliva can heal the wound" (P3).

"...Until I asked my husband to massage me" (P8).

"...Drinking milk... What is... milk from... the mum uung (breast milk booster)." (P6)

"...Drink breast milk booster mom C." (P5)

Participants in this study revealed how the efforts they made based on the obstacles they experienced. Most of the participants have understood the efforts to handle obstacles such as breast milk that does not come out immediately by continuing to do Direct Breast Feeding (DBF), Inverted nipple by doing Hoffman manipulation by pulling the nipple, or breast shield and breast shell. The most efficient thing to improve this situation is the baby's strong direct suction (Alifah, 2023).

Most participants reported experiencing nipple chafing. Nipple chafing is a major problem for mothers who do not continue exclusive breastfeeding due to pain or soreness and poor attachment. Therefore, they treat nipple chafing by using breast milk and baby saliva, using coconut oil, creams, ointments to treat nipple chafing. Correction of position and attachment are the most common empirical recommendations for the management of nipple pain problems (Fauziah, 2022).

The participants here are all working mothers. The workload can affect the stress level of the mother. Another participant revealed that the effort to overcome breastfeeding obstacles for working mothers is to adjust the conditions in the work environment. In addition, other participants overcame these obstacles by getting around the time to express breast milk at work. The results of research conducted (Astawa, 2019) showed that there was a relationship between the mother's employment status and the failure of exclusive breastfeeding.

Participants also revealed other obstacles in breastfeeding, namely engorgement (swollen breasts) which is a serious problem for breastfeeding mothers. To overcome the obstacle of swollen breasts, most participants do compresses with warm water on the breast, breastfeed directly on the breast, and do massage on the breast and back. This is in line with research (Rahayu, 2020) that breast pain can be overcome by breastfeeding on demand as often as possible, hot compresses, cold compresses on the breast before breastfeeding, breast massage, cold compresses on the breast between breastfeeding.

Baby refusal during breastfeeding is also an obstacle for mothers to provide exclusive breastfeeding (Faristasari, 2019). A participant who worked as a nurse tried to overcome this obstacle by increasing the frequency of breastfeeding to familiarize her baby. The efforts they make to increase breast milk production are by using the power pumping method, doing oxytocin massage, and consuming breast milk boosters. This is in line with the statement Indonesian Pediatrician Association, that insufficient breast milk syndrome can be overcome in several ways including increasing the frequency of pumping breast milk even though the baby is full, doing power pumping (breastfeeding the baby while pumping breast milk), and consuming foods that increase breast milk production (Nurita, 2023). Another way to overcome the lack of milk production is oxytocin massage.

Oxytocin massage can increase breast milk production by reducing the blockage of milk production channels so as to facilitate the release of breast milk (Nurainun & Susilowati, 2021).

Theme 5: Breastfeeding support

Breastfeeding mothers need the support of the people around them. In this study, participants received support in the breastfeeding process from their family and work environment. Two sub-themes are found in this section:

1. Sub-theme : Family

"...I pumped for a while so my parents gave me the opportunity to pump" (P7).

"...If we don't have time to hold the child, we give it to our husband first, he helps" (P7).

2. Sub-theme : Work Environment

"...My friends have no problem, I want the pump to be allowed" (P7)

"...Friends are very supportive of pumping, they give us time" (P1).

"...For example, when I'm working... Like being reminded by friends to pump..." (P4)

"...Yes, it is supportive... so for example, suddenly like we are pumping, at most we ask permission from our friends / to the supervisor in charge... oh yes Ra.... Come on please" (P1)

"...Like yes... That... The leader, if for example I work, is temporarily suspended for pumping" (P5).

"... means that a room is provided, more or less lockable." (P5)

Breastfeeding mothers really need the support of the people around them (Salamah, 2019). In this study, participants received support in the breastfeeding process from their family and work environment. According to (Saraha, 2020) family support is a factor that influences success in exclusive breastfeeding. Family support is support to motivate mothers to provide only breast milk to their babies until the age of 6 months, including providing psychological support to mothers and preparing balanced nutrition to mothers (Yazia & Suryani, 2023). breastfeeding requires a stable emotional condition, considering that maternal psychological factors greatly affect milk production.

Work environment support is very helpful for working mothers who are breastfeeding. This support comes from coworkers, leaders, and supportive facilities in the workplace for breastfeeding mothers (Dewi, 2018). Facility support was certainly not obtained by all participants in this study. Nevertheless, the work environment did not prevent them from continuing to provide exclusive breastfeeding to their babies. This is in line with the results of Anggaini & Fitri (2022) research that the success in providing exclusive breastfeeding to working mothers is highly dependent on the environment, especially support from husbands, other family members, coworkers and the community so that mothers can comfortably provide breast milk and care for their children while working.

Government Regulation No. 33/2012 on guaranteeing the implementation of exclusive breastfeeding requires every workplace manager and public facility administrator to enact internal regulations that support and assist the success of breastfeeding programs. Such internal regulations demonstrate the company's support for breastfeeding and enable the company to implement a lactation-friendly workplace policy.

Theme 6 : Emotions

Breastfeeding mothers have strong emotions after giving birth. In this study, participants' emotions were seen in feelings of happiness and anxiety. It can be visualized as follows:

"...Very happy, touched" (P4)

"...After giving birth / returning from the hospital, the milk was quite full, 150 cc for the first PD. So I was really happy there" (P7).

"...Does she have enough milk" (P4)

Breastfeeding mothers have strong emotions after giving birth. In this study, participants' emotions were seen in feelings of happiness and anxiety. Efforts made in providing positive affirmations to mothers who are breastfeeding are very important. This support comes from husbands, families, health workers, and the environment (Kristiyanti, 2020). Efforts by

providing positive affirmations aim to increase self-confidence in mothers and reduce anxiety levels during the breastfeeding process.

Positive affirmations are formed so that the mother believes that she is able to breastfeed happily and that the milk produced is able to meet the needs of her baby. Mothers who feel happy will be able to increase the secretion of endorphine hormone. The endorphin hormone secreted by breastfeeding mothers will trigger the secretion of the hormone oxytocin (Rahayu, 2020). The oxytocin hormone is maximized when the mother is breastfeeding so that the milk secreted will also be abundant and the mother feels happy. So the importance of positive affirmation to breastfeeding mothers is very important to increase self-confidence in mothers and reduce anxiety during the breastfeeding process.

CONCLUSION

The results of research conducted on 8 participants, obtained 6 themes that reveal the experience of breastfeeding in working mothers, namely 1) the process of pregnancy and childbirth, 2) confidence, 3) obstacles to breastfeeding, 4) efforts to overcome breastfeeding obstacles, 5) breastfeeding support, 6) emotions. the process of breastfeeding in working mothers really needs support from family, workplace environment (friends, leaders, facilities). Mothers who receive adequate support increase success in exclusive breastfeeding. It is hoped that the community, especially working mothers, will better understand exclusive breastfeeding, health workers are expected to be able to provide education in the form of counseling related to lactation management, especially for working mothers, and for educational institutions, it is hoped that this research can be a reference for future researchers, then for future researchers it is hoped that they can maximize the results of this study by adding objectives and using different methods so that the results obtained are more varied.

RECOMENDATION

With the right socialization of knowledge, the public can better understand and recognize the changes that occur in working breastfeeding mothers, so that the assistance and support provided can improve the self-abilities of working mothers who are breastfeeding their babies.

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